

Identifying Role of Positive Organizational Climate in Enhancing Job Satisfaction of Teachers: “A Case Study of four top private schools of Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan”

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ABSTRACT

The Qualitative study was conducted in order to identify the role of positive organizational climate in creating Job satisfaction of teachers of four selected schools of khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan. The organizational climate is shared perception of employees of organization in which it works. If climate of organization is positive then it will enhance the satisfaction of teachers. The McGregor Y, theory was applied in study which states “Give water to employees and let them bloom”. The qualitative research methodology was used where data was collected via interviews and survey. The data was analyzed with the help of NVivo 10. The finding shows that work environment, competencies, management effectiveness, team work and compensation are elements of positive organizational climate. The result also shows that management effectiveness contributes more to positive organizational climate than other elements. The finding also shows that these elements of positive organizational climate create job satisfaction of teachers. The management effectiveness creates more job satisfaction as it is most important element of positive organizational climate.

KEY WORDS: Organizational climate, work environment, management effectiveness, competencies, team Work and compensation

INTRODUCTION

In present era, organizations are improving their practices in order to survive in the global market. Different industries like automobile, chemical, pharmaceutical etc. are working on creating positive organizational climate that may enhance job satisfaction of employees. Positive organizational climate is not a new idea but now it becomes prerequisite for organization because it also enhances motivation of employees (Atkinson & Frechette, 2009). The organizations can improve performance through incorporating positive climate in organization. Organizational climate is shared perception of employees that describes the organization in which it works (Ali & Patnaik, 2014).Giri and Kumar (2007) investigated that organizational climate had a significant effect on job satisfaction. The management of schools has given less attention in creating positive organizational climate that may attract and retain teachers. Therefore, this study covered the four top schools of khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan. It was conducted in order to identify the role of positive organizational climate in creating the Job satisfaction of teachers. If teachers are providing with good work environment; and they have ability to perform their job; and management is so effective in identifying the training needs of teachers; and teamwork is appreciated; and they are fairly compensated for their work then it creates positive climate of School that has significant impact on teachers’ Job satisfaction. Schools were selected for study because teachers are very important part of any Nation. Therefore, management should develop the climate of school that satisfies the teachers. If teachers are satisfied then they work with their heart and soul. The study is different because qualitative method was used in collecting and analysing the data. The study is also different because positive organizational climate was studied in support of McGregor Y theory of motivation that may enhance job satisfaction of teachers.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Following are two questions of research that were investigated.

1. At what extend work environment, competency, management effectiveness, teamwork and compensation, create positive organizational Climate?
2. Does Positive organizational climate create Job satisfaction of teachers?

SCOPE OF STUDY

In literature, various dimensions of organizational climate were studied. This study was focused on only five dimensions of organizational climate and their relationship with job satisfaction. It only focused on organizational climate of top four schools of khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Climate

The concept of Organizational climate was first introduced in the late 1940s. After that, in 1968, Stringer had defined organizational Climate as a set of measurable properties of the work environment that is based on the collective perceptions of the employees in the environment and verified to influence their motivation and behavior. Furthermore, perceptions that individuals have of their workplaces is reflected by personal values and psychological desires (McMurray, Merlo, Sarros, & Islam, 2010). Organizational climate plays very important in creating motivating environment for employees (Rusu&Avasilcai, 2014).

Organizational climate is different from organizational culture. Organizational culture is defined as system of shared assumptions, beliefs and values that shapes how people behave in organization while organizational climate is about how members of an organization experience the culture of an organization. Simply, we can say organizational culture is personality of organization while organizational climate is mood of organization. Organizational climate is much easier to measure than organizational culture. (Maclaughlin, 2013).

Researchers have defined organizational climate in different proportions. It has no single definition because it is multi-dimensional concept. The characteristics of organizational climate are:

- It is an abstract and intangible concept. And it has a significant impact on the behaviour and Performance of organizational members
- It is perceived characteristic of internal environment of organization.
- It is relatively enduring characteristics that remain constant over a period.
- It differentiates one organization from other organization because it gives distinct identity to organization.

Researchers used different dimensions of organizational climate depending upon nature of organization.

Litwin and Stringer, defined organization in nine dimensions: structure, reward, responsibility, risk, warmth, support, standard, conflict and identity. Forum's research defines climate in six dimensions (role clarity, commitment, standard, responsibility, recognition and team work) that influence the work environment and employee motivation (Atkinson & Frechette, 2009).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction can be defined by many researchers and practitioners. In 1769, Locke had defined Job satisfaction as a pleasurable emotional feeling resulting from job experience. In 2003, Hulin and Judge have defined job satisfaction as multidimensional psychological response to individual's Job. Job satisfaction enhances the productivity and efficiency of employees. Satisfied employees are main resources for organization (malpani & Varshney, 2014).

Job Satisfaction is of two types. First type of job satisfaction is related to overall feelings of employee about their jobs that is called Global job satisfaction. Second type is Facet satisfaction that is related feeling of specific job aspects. (Redmond & Kuffour, 2014). Simply, Job satisfaction depends upon individuals' feeling of what is important for them (Wengrzyn, 2013).

Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction

Researchers stated that Workload intensity and role ambiguity are two components of Poor organizational climate that led nurses to depart many caring practices (performance) in hospital surroundings. They conducted mixed-method study in which they combined nurse surveys (N=292) with a qualitative case study of 15 direct-care registered nurses (RNs), nursing personnel and managers. They concluded that organized interventions are required to get better organizational climate and to support RNs' involvement in a full range of caring practices (G, CA, & SP, 2014).

Researchers conducted qualitative research to identify the role of organizational climate of elementary schools on job satisfaction of Elementary teachers. They concluded, organizational climate has not significant impact on job satisfaction of teachers but principal should create healthy climate of school that enhances the performance of teachers. Principal should demonstrate leadership behavior. They recommended that organizational climate can be improved through cooperation, mutual understanding faithfulness, dignity of work. (Rani & Rani, 2014).

Researchers conducted Qualitative research in which 12 nurses were selected through purposive sampling and data was collected via deep interviews with semi-structural questions. Data was analyzed through conventional content analysis. The Research concluded that nurses practiced their workplace as non-supportive because of poor organizational climate, low social dignity, poor work conditions, and managers' unawareness to individual and professional values were measured as inhibitory factors to support. (sodeify, vanaki, & Mohammadi, 2013)

Researchers stated that employee's attitude towards organization; organizational climate and employee's engagement are major antecedents of organizational citizenship behavior. They tested this relationship with the help of the structural equation modeling (SEM) and AMOS graphic. (Allameh, Shahriari, & Mansoori, 2012).

Researcher studied impact of various ethical climate types and job satisfaction on organizational commitment at a Chinese Private Construction company. Caring and independence types of ethical climate had a significant positive impact on organizational commitment (Fu &

Deshpande, 2012).

Researcher conducted empirical study and concluded that organizational climate had significant effects on human resources management effectiveness (turnover intention, job satisfaction and work efficacy). Organizational climate also had significant effects on organization like commitment and collective identity of employees. (Zhang, 2010)

Researchers used Structural Equation Modeling to analyze the data that was collected from a sample of HR managers in Multinational Corporation in Hong Kong. They concluded that that top management support for equal opportunities (fairness) is positively related to Family Friendly Work Practices (FFWPs) and organizational Climate. The Organizational Climate is also served as intermediate between FFWPs and Outcomes. (NGO, Foley, & Loi, 2009)

Researcher conducted empirical study to investigate the effect of nine organizational ethical climates on work satisfaction in a cultural context of developing countries. The nine organizational ethical climates were self-interest, company profit, efficiency, friendship, team interest, social responsibility, personal morality, company rules and procedures, and laws and professional codes. Researcher concluded that self-interest have negative effect on work satisfaction while remaining ethic type climates have positive effect on work satisfaction. (Elci&Alpkan, 2008)

Researchers stated that psychological capital is positively related to performance, satisfaction and commitment. Organizational supportive climate is related to employees' satisfaction and commitment. (Luthans, Norman, Avolio, & Avey, 2008)

Theoretical Framework

McGregor theory Y of motivation applied in this research. Theory Y stated, "Give employees water and let them bloom" (Stewart, 2010). So, if managers create positive organizational climate then employees are motivated towards the work because they are fully satisfied with their Job.

Research Hypothesis

H1: Work environment, competency, management effectiveness, teamwork and compensation are very important elements in creating positive organizational climate.

H2: There is significant relationship between positive organizational climate and Job satisfaction

H2a: There is significant relationship between compensation and Job satisfaction.

H2b: There is significant relationship between competencies and Job satisfaction

H2c: There is significant relationship between management effectiveness and Job satisfaction.

H2d: There is significant relationship between team work and Job satisfaction

H2e: There is significant relationship between team work and Job satisfaction

METHODOLOGY

The qualitative research methodology was used in this study.

Sample of Study

For the purpose of qualitative study, only four top schools of khairpur were selected. A sample of 35 teachers was included in this study. It did not include administrative staffs of schools.

Data Collection Techniques

Data was collected via in-depth interviews and survey from teachers of selected schools of khairpur, Sindh Pakistan. Out of 35 teachers, face to face interviews were conducted from 15 teachers, ranging in length from 45 minutes to an hour. The survey was conducted from remaining teachers.

The structured questionnaire was used in survey.

Independent Variable

The questions of organizational climate were taken from the article of (Gupta, 2008). I took only five dimensions of organizational climate from that article. The reliability of instrument was checked via SPSS 16. The Cronbach Alpha value of instrument is 0.927 that shows its reliability.

Dependent Variable

The questions related to Job satisfaction was taken from article of (Saleem, Mahmood, & Mahmood, 2010). The Cronbach's Alpha value of Job satisfaction scale is 0.957.

In interview, open-ended questions were asked from teachers of selected schools. The themes of questions were same as of structured questionnaires of survey but in interview; respondents were free to give their opinions.

Data Analyze Technique

Due to qualitative nature of research, the NVivo 10 software was used in this study. The NVivo10 converts unorganized data into organized form via nodes and coding of data.

Nodes and Coding

In NVivo, nodes were formed and data were coded in their respective nodes. In this paper, two main node(Organizational climate and Teachers' Job Satisfaction) were formed. Organizational Climate had five child nodes namely compensation, competencies, management effectiveness, team work and work environment.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Queries

The three queries of NVivo 10 were run in order to get results. Three queries were Word Frequency Query, Text Search Query and Matrix Coding Query.

Word Frequency Query

The word frequency query was run in order to see which word was frequently used in nodes. The findings showed that respondents frequently used the words like work, management, team, environment, compensation and Job. The word cloud of word frequency query is shown in appendix.

Text Search Query

The text search query was run in order to see the link between different sentences over one word. The text search query was run on organizational climate and job satisfaction themes. The tree map of text search query of themes is shown in appendix.

Matrix Coding Query

The proposed hypothesis were tested by applying Matrix Coding Query. The cell content option was used to get results.

H1: Work environment, competency, management effectiveness, teamwork and compensation are very important elements in creating positive organizational climate.

The finding shows that work environment, competencies, management effectiveness, teamwork and compensation are elements of positive organizational climate. Therefore, these elements can create positive organizational climate. The result also shows that management effectiveness contributes more to positive organizational climate than other elements. Its means management itself is very important part in creating good climate of schools that may enhance the productivity of school. The Node matrix result is shown in appendix.

H2: There is significant relationship between positive organizational climate and Job satisfaction

H2a: There is significant relationship between compensation and Job satisfaction.

H2b: There is significant relationship between competencies and Job satisfaction

H2c: There is significant relationship between management effectiveness and Job satisfaction.

H2d: There is significant relationship between team work and Job satisfaction

H2e: There is significant relationship between team work and Job satisfaction

The finding of Hypothesis II is shown in appendix. The positive organizational climate can create the job

satisfaction of teachers of selected schools of Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan. So schools should give attention to these five elements of organizational climate which may affect the Job satisfaction of teachers. The result shows that management effectiveness is vital element in creating job satisfaction of teachers.

LIMITATION

This study is constrained to four schools of khairpur, Sindh Pakistan. The climate of organization may change from one industry to another industry. These five dimensions of organizational climate can be tested in different industries. Similarly, remaining dimensions of organizational climate can be tested for creating positive climate of schools and their impact on job satisfaction of teachers.

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APPENDIX

WORD CLOUD OF WORD FREQUENCY QUERY

TREE MAP OF TEXT SEARCH QUERY (ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE)

TREE MAP OF TEXT SEARCH QUERY (JOB SATISFACTION)

	Compensation	Competencies	Management Effectiveness	Team Work	work Environment
1 : organizational climate	14.38%	24.18%	27.37%	18.77%	15.3%

HYPOTHESIS 1: NODE MATRIX OF MATRIX CODING QUERY

HYPOTHESIS 2: NODE MATRIX OF MATRIX CODING QUERY

	Job Satisfaction
1 : organizational climate	100%

HYPOTHESIS 2A, 2B, 2C, 2D & 2E: NODE MATRIX OF MATRIX CODING QUERY

	Job Satisfaction
1 : Compensation	17.88%
2 : Competencies	21.58%
3 : Management Effectiveness	22.78%
4 : Team Work	19.53%
5 : work environment	18.23%